

METHODOLOGY FOR INCREASING THE POSSIBILITIES OF USING INDEPENDENT LEARNING TASKS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF STUDENTS' COGNITIVE ACTIVITY

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Abstract: The article presents the organization of independent work for elementary school students in mathematics, the factors that are important for the teacher to pay attention to when organizing independent work, and the requirements for independent work conducted in mathematics classes. .

Key words: Primary class, teacher, student, task, independent work, education, method.

Introduction.

The direction of positive work carried out in the continuous education system introduced in our country is sufficiently noted in the Law on Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan, and in the National Personnel Training Program. The specified directions set high tasks for all levels of continuous education.

It is noted that it is necessary to make effective use of universal and national cultural values and arm them with new techniques and technologies in order to make the young people who are our future heirs a perfect human being. The complex tasks assigned to educational institutions, teachers, educators and parents are of state importance, and by putting them into practice, it is possible to improve the technology of education and training, to ensure that the continuity of education works as a thorough and compact system. can be provided.

It is necessary to pay special attention to the means of ensuring the physical, moral and mental maturity of the students of the educational system. Therefore, acquiring knowledge and professional training requires independent thinking and mental activity from the student, who is considered both an object and a subject of education. Any educational process is a complex pedagogical system that represents the relationship between parents, teachers and students.

Literature analysis and methodology.

About the role of educational processes in the expansion of cognitive activity in psychology, the French scientist J. Godefroy's book "What is psychology" in 2 volumes states that since the ancient world, the human psyche, its heart, feelings, behavior issues have been in the center of attention, psychology is a science In its development, the views of philosophers, the development of natural sciences, the separation of various sciences from the science of philosophy since the 17th century, the approaches of Condillac and Locke in the 18th and 19th centuries have been justified. The contribution of the German psychologist and physiologist Wilhelm Wundt from 1832 to 1920 in the development of the cognitive processes of psychology, the organization and nature of special experimental testing laboratories was revealed by him. The Russian psychologist R.S. Nemov consists of three volumes - in the book

of psychology, it is written that the term psychology was first used in the 16th century, that through consciousness and self-observation, a person began to study mental states in himself, and later to study these mental processes in the field of human activity. explained that it was necessary.

In these cases, students get to know each other and communicate. Children's cognitive activities are a unit of emotional perception, theoretical thinking and practical activity. It arises at every stage of education and develops regularly. Cognitive activity is strengthened in all types of social relations and educational activities of students. In addition, it is important for students to perform certain tasks in educational processes in the expansion of cognitive activity.

In the dictionary of pedagogical terms, knowledge is defined as follows:

- ❖ *level of mastery of the educational material presented to pupils and students during the educational process;*
- ❖ *it is the process of learning, mastering, acquiring existence and its objective laws.*

So, in the process of cognitive activity, the student absorbs the presented knowledge and fully understands the surrounding reality.

It is known that there are many signs and characteristics of things and events in the external world that surround us. For example, things' color, taste, smell, hardness or softness, roughness or flatness, temperature, etc. We also reflect various signs and characteristics of these things and events in our minds through our senses.

Various signs and characteristics of things and events around us always affect our sense organs. As a result, we have different sensations. For example, the sense of sight as a result of the impact of rays on our eyes, the sense of hearing as a result of the impact of air waves of different speeds and voltages on our ears, the sense of hearing as a result of the impact of air waves on our ears during breathing as a result of the impact of various particles of matter, the sense of smell, as a result of touching something with our hands or body, skin (tactile - something touching our skin) or pressure sensation, and similar sensations are always formed.

So, by intuition, we say that as a result of the direct impact of objects and events around us on our sense organs, some of their signs and characteristics are reflected in our brain.

Intuition is a simple psychological process among cognitive processes, and it reflects things and events in the external world. It reflects certain signs and characteristics and the internal state of the organism through the direct impact of stimuli from the external world on specific receptors. It is known that the initial stage of human perception begins with emotional cognition, and then it passes to logical cognition. Since intuition is also a simple psychological process, its occurrence does not occur by itself. These include:

- Existence of things and events that affect the sense organs.
- Availability of a sensing device, that is, an analyzer.

For example, we feel the coldness of the air, the hardness of iron, the softness of snow, etc.

Sensation is related to perception, but before perceiving an object or phenomenon, it is necessary to perceive it, so sensations are the result of the effect of matter on our sense organs. It receives, selects and collects sensory information, receives and processes the flow of information every second and delivers it to the brain. As a result, the environment is an

adequate reflection of the surrounding external world and the body's internal state. The sense organs are one of the ways that the external world enters the human mind.

In the educational process, it is necessary to create favorable conditions for the development of voluntary, stable, strong, strong, active conscious attention in students of junior school age. In the process of learning, voluntary, conscious attention is formed with the help of independent mental activity, examples, problem solving, didactic exercises, repetition. 7-8-year-old children develop the skills of voluntary concentration, distribution, and conscious control of attention.

Elementary school students can develop their activities independently to a certain extent. They verbally describe the consistency of their plans and actions. With the help of planning, the voluntary attention of students develops content. Involvement of students of junior school age in cognitive activities requires different methods of mental activity. The educational process plays an important role in the formation of the activity of enriching the knowledge reserves of students with the help of their imagination about the material world.

For example, it is useless to teach a child to think logically without being logical. The main activities of school children are as follows:

- *Learning by subject;*
- *Individual and object games, role-playing games with a collective plot;*
- *Individual and group creativity;*
- *Competition games;*
- *Relationship games;*
- *Livelihood work.*

The importance of these games in children's cognitive processes is great. Experts believe that the development of a person is related to the material world, and the way of life of a person determines his consciousness. Educational activities play an important role in human development during childhood. The expansion of the students' cognitive activity is primarily the result of their assimilation of scientific phenomena, thoughts, ideas, evidence, and the social experience of the people. The interrelationship of development and teaching in the science of pedagogy has its own historical development path. At first, pedagogues put forward the idea that the development of students takes place by itself. After identifying the impact of education on development, they noted that this impact is involuntary. In addition, personal views on the problem of education and mental development of students have emerged.

The main essence of this point of view is that a well-organized educational process accelerates the student's development. Education is built not only in completed series. Based on this approach, the theory of active, individual, differentiated approach to education in pedagogy was created. There is no uniformity in the process of personality development.

For elementary school students, this time is a period of intellectual development based on figurative thinking. This is mainly done in the educational process. Other aspects of the personality do not develop during the learning process. We try to establish the direction of development that leads to students. The basis of self-esteem in intellectual development is the personal positive experience of students. This is manifested in the educational process.

Observations show that most students do not have this experience. Dissatisfaction with the result of one's work cannot be the basis of students' self-esteem. One of the laws that occupy an important place in this direction is the expansion of cognitive activity of students in certain educational situations, personal equality and self-respect.

The mistakes made in the process of learning, manifested through the activities of students, have a certain impact on the student's mood and development. In the process of organizing students' cognitive activities, the teacher should ask himself the question of how to expand this activity. As a result of the analysis of the available scientific sources and the observations made, the students' cognitive activity consists of the following components:

- knowledge interests;
- educational goals;
- emotions: personal anxiety and emotional stability;
- the need to achieve and communicate;
- intellectual ability and openness to communication;
- personal experiences and skills.

In the studies devoted to the development of cognitive activity in the learning process, ensuring the activity of students based on their independence is divided into three directions.

- imitative based on a sample;
- visibility-based enforcement;
- creative cognitive activity.

Imitative activity is formed on the basis of ready-made examples of movement. Ideally, it encourages students to be diligent on the basis of objectivity. Research-based executive activity consists of independently searching for ways to solve problem situations proposed by the teacher in a comparative way with research activity. Creative activity, as a higher form of cognitive activity, can be used to search for new, original ways of solving problems, to show high indicators of independent management of one's own behavior, and this level can be compared with personal activity.

Discussion and results:

Cognitive activity in traditional educational conditions is understood as a teacher's action aimed at students' acquisition of ready knowledge. Experts gradually began to understand the need to move to new levels of cognitive activity. Experts were able to theoretically justify that at first a certain part of knowledge, and later all information should not be transferred to students in a ready form. It is intended to achieve that a certain part of the information provided by the teacher to the students on the basis of communication will be the basis for independent research.

Generalized cognitive skills do not arise by themselves when educational processes aimed at the development of cognitive activity are designed. Because in this process, goal-oriented special learning situations are realized. In addition, an important component of preparing students to acquire generalized skills is the formation of special educational and cognitive skills in them.

In the development of the student's cognitive activity, educational situations have a special didactic significance. Educational activity is a tool with the help of which the student tries to master the content of the educational subject. The student's activity is directed to mastering the content of the educational subject. It is known that the teacher creates a situation of managing the student's activity. This process continues until the student has the opportunity to independently manage his activities. In this process, the teacher's task is to take into account the student's inclinations, plan, control and correct his activities. Learning gives the student confidence in his behavior. Acquiring this confidence is carried out in the process of primary education. This is achieved by developing the student's cognitive activity.

It can be seen that most of the students are not trying to expand their knowledge. They do not actively participate in classes, they are more interested in their free activities outside the educational process. Finding and eliminating the reasons for this is one of the priority issues of pedagogy. While going to school, students try to win the love and attention of teachers and classmates.

According to the pedagogues, the student's success increases his interest in educational activities. Interest in reading arises only when students are encouraged by the successful acquisition of knowledge. If the student feels joy in the process of his work, if he is proud of overcoming difficulties, he starts to look at the learning process with special interest. That's why the teacher should create a situation for students to enjoy learning. It is necessary to instill in the hearts of students a sense of pride and a sense of worthiness of their success. Success is ensured by creating a learning environment that is conducive for every student to achieve. Experts emphasize that meeting the student's cognitive needs in the educational situation plays an important role in his development. If the student is given the opportunity to succeed in the educational situation, he will be able to choose the right path in life.

Conclusions and suggestions:

In short, they are trying to justify in every way that the creation of an educational situation creates ample opportunities for the development of the student's cognitive activity. If students seek to know, feel the need to learn, they will develop healthy inclinations and interests, and they will succeed in the process of learning.

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